

Effective photocatalytic demineralization of reactive red 198 utilizing nanocomposite particles under UV light irradiation

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Abstract : The present paper discusses the synthesis and characterization of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles for the photodegradation of azo dye in wastewater. Nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles synthesized by sol-gel process and XRD analysis used to investigate the structure and crystallite size distribution of composite particles. The photocatalytic activity of composite particles was evaluated using reactive red 198 as a model pollutant. The effect of wavelength of UV light on the photocatalytic degradation and the photodegradability of dye in nanocomposite particles were measured. The effects of operating parameters such as pH, catalyst loading and concentration of dye solution have been investigated. The photodegradation of dye solution follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The reusability of the nanocomposite particles has also been investigated.

Keywords : Nanocomposite particles, azo dye, pollutant, photodegradability, photocatalyst.

Introduction

Water pollutants create significant environmental problems around the globe. Over the last decade environmental pollution remediation became a national and global priority. As a response, the development of newer eco-friendly methods of destroying these pollutants became an imperative task. Recent reports reveal that large amounts of colored dye wastewaters released into environment mainly by dyestuff and textile industry lead to severe surface water and groundwater contamination^{1,2}. Several color-causing substances are micro toxic to aquatic biota and adverse effect on the environment and are the dramatic source of aesthetic pollution, eutrophication and disturbance in aquatic life due to their toxicity and persistence. As international environmental standards are becoming more stringent, technological systems for the removal of such dyes have been developed^{3,4}. Nowadays the scientific and engineering interest in the application of semiconductor photocatalysis has grown exponentially⁵. One promising technique for destroying organic contaminants in the textile wastewater is the application of photocatalysts⁶. Photocatalysis has proved to be of real interest as efficient tool for degrading both aquatic and atmospheric organic contaminants⁷. It involves the

acceleration of photoreaction in presence of semiconductor photocatalyst and one of the major applications is photocatalytic oxidation (PCO) to effect partial or total mineralisation of gas phase or liquid phase contaminants to benign substances. The term 'photocatalytic degradation' usually refers to complete photocatalytic oxidation or photomineralisation of dye molecule to CO₂, H₂O, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻ and halide ions⁸. Some semiconductors, such as nanosized TiO₂ or ZnO, have attracted extensive attention as a photocatalyst for the degradation of organic pollutants in water and air under UV irradiation^{9,10}. ZnO can act as a sensitizer for light-induced redox due to its electronic structure, which is characterized by a filler valence band and an empty conduction band. The nanosized ZnO with the features of large volume to area ratio, high ultraviolet (UV) absorption and long life-span has been widely used as catalyst¹¹, gas sensor¹², active filler for rubber and plastic, UV absorber in cosmetics and anti-virus agent in coating¹³. ZnO nanoparticles can be synthesized by various approaches including sol-gel processing¹⁴, homogeneous precipitation¹⁵, mechanical milling¹⁶, organo metallic synthesis¹⁷, microwave method¹⁸, spray pyrolysis¹⁹, thermal evaporation²⁰ and mechano chemical synthesis²¹. Nano TiO₂ has become

the most widely investigated semiconductor in both alternative energy and environmental remediation research fields because of its availability, non-toxic nature and photostability. Today, it is used to purify water and air, control odors, and sterilize²². ZnO appears to be suitable alternative to TiO₂ since its photodegradation mechanism has been proven to be similar to that of TiO₂²³. Nano TiO₂ which has a band gap of 3.2 eV²⁴ is superior to other semiconductor oxides due to its high chemical stability, low cost and non-toxic nature. ZnO which has a similar band gap of nano TiO₂ about 3.2 eV due to its high quantum efficiency²⁵. Under UV light irradiation both TiO₂ and ZnO are highly efficient photocatalysts since their photogenerated electrons and holes are highly oxidizing and reducing agents respectively²⁶. ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite particles have also been used as promising photocatalyst and also in the field of photo electrochemical application²⁷. Recently, extensive investigations have been concentrated on the synthesis and environmental applications of nanocomposite metal oxides such as ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite particle to improve the quantum efficiency of photocatalysts for applications in water purification. This is due to the high reactivity of TiO₂ and the large binding energy of ZnO, which improve the process of electron and hole transfer between the corresponding conduction and valence bands. The ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite particle via sol-gel process has advantages of higher surface activity due to the nanoparticles being not conglomerated and easily reclaimed after reaction. The preparation of ZnO-TiO₂ nano composite particle by sol-gel process has notable advantages such as high purity, good uniformity in the structure, low-temperature synthesis and easily controlled reaction compared to other methods²⁸.

Present work :

In this paper, we prepared the nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle by sol-gel method and studied the crystallite size by XRD method. The photocatalytic activity of the nanophotocatalyst was investigated by taking reactive red 198 as model compound. The effect of pH, the effect of catalyst weight and the effect of concentration of dye solution in the photocatalytic degradation studies has been observed.

Materials and methods :

Apparatus and reagents :

Zinc acetate dihydrate, oxalic acid dihydrate, titanium(IV) isopropoxide, glacial acetic acid, diethanolamine, ethanol and all the organic reagents were analytical grade purchased from Merck, SRL, Qualigens, India. Double distilled water was used for all the measurements. ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle was prepared by sol-gel method and the brief of procedure is as follows. Titanium(IV) isopropoxide was dissolved in ethanol and stirred for 10 min at 70 °C in a water bath to get precursor solution. The zinc acetate was added to get this precursor solution containing both Ti and Zn. A mixture of distilled water, diethanolamine and ethanol was dropped into the solution at a speed of one drop per second under a strong stirring for 2 h to achieve a transparent ZnO-TiO₂ sol in the magnetic stirrer. It was gelled, dried and crushed into fine powder and calcined at 500 °C for 5 h. Then it cooled to get nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles.

Characterization of nano photocatalyst :

The XRD analysis was done to analyze the crystallite size of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles. Sample for powder X-ray Diffraction (XRD) was prepared by making a thin film of powder with ethanol on a glass plate and the measurement was performed with a Rigaku Geiger flex X-ray diffractometer with Ni-filtered CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$, 30 kV, 15 mA). The XRD patterns were recorded in the range of 20–80°, with a scan speed of 2°/min and the crystallite size was calculated using the Scherrer equation. Cary-50 ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Varian) was used in measurements of absorbance of the dye solution at different catalyst weight, different pH and different concentration at an incident wavelength, λ_{max} , of 532 nm.

Photocatalytic reactor :

The photodegradation study of dye solution was carried out in a suspended particle vertical catalytic reactor in the batch mode. In this nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle was suspended in the solution column through aeration. The typical experimental procedure consisted of aerating a mixture of 250 ml of dye solution of known concentration and the photocatalyst for 30 min to allow

pre-adsorption followed by irradiation with the UV light. The lamp emits 8W of UV radiation with a peak wavelength of 254 nm. Samples of 3 ml were withdrawn at periodic intervals of irradiation time followed by centrifugation. The residual concentration of dye solution was measured at 532 nm using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer. After the analysis the solutions were returned to the reactor. All the studies have been carried out at 30 °C and the pH of the solution has been adjusted to desired values between 4.0 and 10.0 by using dilute solutions of HCl or NaOH.

Results and discussion

XRD pattern of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles :

Fig. 1 shows XRD diffraction graph for nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles. The nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle exhibits the anatase phase for TiO₂ and sphalerite phase for ZnO. It can be seen that both the phase composition and the crystallinity of the composite particles altered obviously with the calcinating temperature. In the presence of air the ZnO-TiO₂ composite powder was rather amorphous after 2 h calcination at 500 °C. With the increase of calcinations time from 2 to 5 h, the composite powder crystallized well and the resultant diffraction peaks were quite sharp. The XRD patterns showed that the nano TiO₂ was identified as an anatase-phase (JCPDF 21-1272) and it is confirmed by peaks appearing at 2θ : 37.0, 37.8, 54.0, 55.2, 68.9 correspond to the diffraction patterns of (1 0 3), (0 0 4), (1 0 5), (2 1 1) and (1 1 6). Nano ZnO

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles.

(JCPDF 36-1451) corresponds to zincite-phase and it is confirmed by peaks appearing at 2θ : 31.7, 36.2, 47.5, 56.5, 66.4 and 67.9 correspond to the diffraction patterns of (1 0 0), (1 0 1), (1 1 0), (1 0 3), (1 1 2) and (2 0 1) respectively²⁹. The crystal sizes of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles are 4.9 nm, 5 nm and 4.4 nm from the 3 different main diffraction peaks and the average crystallite size was calculated to be around 5–10 nm. This XRD result indicates the successful preparation of ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite particles by sol-gel method and clearly shows that Ti is in interaction with the Zn. Also the nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles are formed with mixture of single agglomerates of anatase, zincite or zinc titanium oxide.

Effect of incident wavelength on the photocatalytic degradation :

The photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198 has been investigated by exposing the dye solution to UV light of incident wavelength 254 nm in the presence of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles. A sample of 50 μM of the dye solution on irradiation with 254 nm, dye has been found to undergo complete mineralization in 100 min. Under similar conditions with 375 nm incident wavelength of light, only 40% of the degradation has been observed. The effect of incident light wavelength on the photodegradability of reactive red 198 as a function of time is shown in Fig. 2 and the experimental data is given in Table 1. The improved effectiveness of 254 nm light compared to 375 nm light may be due to the shorter

Fig. 2. Effect of wavelength of incident light on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198.

Table 1. Effect of wavelength of incident light on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198

Time (m)	Reactive red 198 dyeconcentration in μM	
	1	2
Before adsorption	50	50
0	46.7	46.7
5	25.4	43.8
10	15.9	41.1
15	9.7	40
20	6.6	39.3
30	3	37.5
40	1.7	35.2
50	0.4	31.3
60	0	28.1

[Reactive red 198] = 50 μM ; pH = 7.0 ± 0.1 ; temperature = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; nanophotocatalyst = ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles (1.0 g/L); absorbance measured at 532 nm : (1) Reactive red 198 irradiated with UV light of wavelength 254 nm. (2) Reactive red 198 irradiated with UV visible light of wavelength 375 nm.

wavelength light is absorbed more strongly by the nanophotocatalyst than the longer wavelength light. The penetration distance of photons into the particle is shorter and photoelectrons and holes are formed closer to the surface of the particle. Therefore they take less time to migrate to the surface of the particle and have less time to participate in energy wasting recombination reactions before the surface reaction starts. Many organic molecules are excited by 254 nm light and are degraded by direct action. But the direct degradation process is very less compared to the process in the presence of a photocatalyst. Similar observation has been reported by Mathews and McEvoy³⁰. Therefore the photocatalytic decolourization studies have been carried out at an incident light of wavelength 254 nm.

Photodegradability of reactive red 198 using nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle :

The photodegradability of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles was evaluated using fixed amount of the catalyst (1 g/L) and fixed concentration of the dye (100 μM) at pH 7 is given in Table 2. In addition to experiments with the photocatalyst and irradiation, blank experiments were carried out in the presence of UV light irradiation with the absence of photocatalyst and in the absence of UV light irradiation with the photocatalyst. In the ab-

Table 2. Photodegradability of reactive red 198

Time (m)	Concentration of the reactive red 198 in μM undergoing photocatalytic degradation		
	1	2	3
Before adsorption	100.0	100.0	100.0
0	100	96.4	96.43
5	100	96.7	92.23
10	100	96.6	85.75
15	100	96.5	80.5
25	100	96.5	74.45
35	100	96.4	68.37
45	100	96.4	62.5
60	100	96.3	56.34
75	100	96.2	50.87
90	100	96.1	46.25
105	100	95.9	42.5
120	100	95.8	38.87
135	100	95.7	34.45
150	100	95.7	28.12
165	100	95.6	22
180	100	95.6	15.12
195	100	95.5	8.56
210	100	95.4	0

[Reactive red 198] = 100 μM ; pH = 7.0 ± 0.1 ; temperature = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; nanophotocatalyst = ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle (1.0 g/L); incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 532 nm.

sence of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles or UV irradiation, no observable loss of dye could be seen whereas a slight decrease in pH was observed at the end of experiment which may be due to the generation of proton during the course of reaction³¹. Under the experimental condition complete degradation of the dye solution occurred within 210 min of irradiation using nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles due to its large surface area and unique structure to absorb UV light is shown in Fig. 3. In a photocatalytic process, electron-hole pairs are generated which must be trapped in order to avoid recombination. The hydroxyl ions (OH⁻) are the likely traps for holes, leading to the formation of hydroxyl radicals which are strong oxidant agents, while the traps for electrons are adsorbed oxygen species, leading to the formation of superoxide species (O²⁻) which are unstable, reactive³². The photodegradability of dye solution is influenced by the active site and the photo absorption of the catalyst

Fig. 3. Photodegradability of reactive red 198 using ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite particle.

used. The photocatalytic activity is mainly due to the presence of the intimately bonded ZnO-TiO₂ surface hetero-structure, which promotes the separation of the photogenerated electrons and holes and thus decreases the electron-hole pair recombination rate. In addition to that the degradation rate is directly proportional to the probability of formation of hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]) on the catalyst surface and the probability of hydroxyl radicals reacting with the dye molecules³³.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH is one of the most important parameter for the degradation of reactive red 198 in the presence of nano ZnO-TiO₂. Effect of pH on the photodegradation of reactive red 198 was investigated over the range of 3.0, natural (5.7), 7.0, 8.0 and 10.0 as shown in Fig. 4 and the experimental data is given in Table 3. The dye

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198.

Table 3. Effect of pH on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198

Time (m)	Reactive red 198 concentration in µM on irradiation at different pH values				
	pH 3	pH 5.6	pH 7	pH 8	pH 10
Before adsorption	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
0	96.71	96.1	97.8	97.1	96.5
5	85.67	87.55	89.43	92.65	92
10	75	78.31	82.76	84.45	88.87
15	63.86	70.76	77.12	80.56	83.67
25	52.32	62.56	68.2	73.37	77.6
35	44.35	53.93	61.71	67.78	71.93
45	37.3	45.28	56.16	61.23	66.57
60	26.86	35.76	47.55	52.55	60.87
75	18.25	25.08	40.06	46.1	54.71
90	10.55	16.52	34.28	40.54	47.83
105	4.05	8.37	28.63	34.25	40.24
120	0	2.96	20.97	28.45	34.38
135	0	0	15.55	21.87	27.05
150	0	0	9.6	14.87	18.67
165	0	0	0	10.3	11.67
180	0	0	0	5.08	5.78
195	0	0	0	0.89	0
210	0	0	0	0	0
Initial rate (µM/m)	2.208	1.71	1.674	0.89	0.91

[Reactive red 198] = 100 µM; nanophotocatalyst = ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles (1.0 g/L); temperature = 30.0±0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 532 nm.

wastewater from textile industries usually has a wide range of pH values. When pH > 5.0, the percentage of degradation is stable; while pH < 5.0, the percentage of degradation decreases. At pH values higher than 4.0, the surface becomes negative charge, and the opposite occurs for pH values greater than pH_{pzc}. At pH 5.6, the photodegradation reaction was fast and completed within 135 min, whereas at pH of the dye solutions are 3.0 and 7.0 the degradation reaction was completed within 105 min and at pH 8.0 and 10.0 the degradation process completed within 120 and 150 min. A steady increase in the degradation of dye solution is observed from pH 3.0 to 5.7 and followed by a slow decrease at neutral pH. By increasing pH degradation process performed slowly and increased the process at pH 10.0. It is due to the fact that higher pH value can provide higher concentration of hy-

droxyl ions to react with holes (h^+) to form hydroxyl radicals (OH^-), subsequently enhancing the photodegradation rate of dye solution.

Effect of catalyst loading :

Fig. 5 shows the photodegradation of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles observed by the amount of nanophotocatalyst varying from 0.75 mg/L to 2.5 g/L at fixed concentration of reactive red 198 (100 μ M) in aqueous solution at pH 7. Adequate loading of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles increase the generation rate of electron/hole pairs for enhancing the degradation of pol-

Fig. 5. Effect of catalyst loading on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198.

lutants. At lower loading levels of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle such as 0.75 g/L, photonic adsorption controls the reaction extent due to the limited catalyst surface area and catalyst loading greatly enhances the process performance and it had undergone the complete demineralization at 210 min and the experimental data is given in Table 4. The 1.0 g/L of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle showed 100% of degradation at 190 min whereas 1.5 g/L of nanocatalyst showed photodegradation completely at 165 min. This is due to an increased number of catalytic sites available for adsorption on the surface of nanocatalyst. Also 2.0 g/L and 2.5 g/L weight of the nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle showed complete degradation at 150 and 120 min. At higher loading levels, light scattering by nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle attenuates light absorption inside the reaction medium. This is probably due to the fact that an increased number of available adsorption and catalytic sites on nano ZnO-TiO₂.

Table 4. Effect of catalyst weight on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198

Time (m)	Dye concentration in μ M on irradiation at different weights of nano ZnO-TiO ₂ composite particle					
	Before adsorption	750 mg/L	1 g/L	1.5 g/L	2 g/L	2.5 g/L
0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
5	97	96.5	95	94.5	94	
10	93.89	90.43	89.45	89.84	82.65	
15	88.67	84.76	81.76	77.24	71.29	
25	84.45	79.12	74.68	69.45	63.76	
35	79.34	73.2	66.23	60.5	53.12	
45	72.78	67.71	59.48	50.39	44.21	
60	66.67	61.5	52.4	44.56	38.64	
75	60.47	54.42	46.32	37.03	30.09	
90	54.23	48.35	39.25	31.34	22.67	
105	49.07	42.82	31.78	22.09	13.67	
120	42.65	37.22	25.92	15.04	5	
135	36.81	31.97	18.2	8.98	0	
150	30.81	26.1	10.98	1	0	
165	25.28	20.89	2.09	0	0	
180	19.08	13.08	0	0	0	
195	12.09	5	0	0	0	
210	4.98	0	0	0	0	
Initial rate (μ M/m)	3.11	1.214	1.11	0.932	2.27	

[Reactive red 198] = 100 μ M; pH = 7.0 ± 0.1 ; nanophotocatalyst = ZnO-TiO₂; temperature = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 532 nm.

Effect of dye concentration :

The photocatalytic demineralization experiments on the effect of concentration of reactive red 198 were carried out using fixed amount of nano ZnO-TiO₂ (1 g/L) at pH 7.0 with varying concentrations from 50–120 μ M as shown in Fig. 6. Photocatalytic degradation decreases the number of reactive sites on nano ZnO-TiO₂ and higher degradation levels were observed when initial dye concentration was low. In this experiment, at the initial concentrations 50 μ M and 75 μ M the rate of degradation of reactive red 198 dye solution was fast and completed within 145 and 175 min and the values are given in Table 5. The increased initial dye concentration enhanced the rate of the liquid phase, surface reaction and the initial steps of the degradation reaction mechanism. Here the number of catalytic sites will not be a limiting factor and

Fig. 6. Effect of concentration of dye solution on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198.

Table 5. Effect of dye concentration on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198

Time (m)	Dye concentration in μM on irradiation at differential concentrations				
	50 μM	75 μM	90 μM	100 μM	120 μM
Before adsorption	50.0	75.0	90.0	100.0	120.0
0	48.25	73.45	87.3	97.43	115.34
5	44.64	69.43	82.56	92.23	110.65
10	39.62	64.65	77.23	85.75	104.45
15	35.43	60.75	72	80.5	98.56
25	30.76	54.37	66.37	74.45	92.12
35	26.75	49.62	60.75	68.37	86.54
45	22.34	44.62	54.75	62.5	81.34
60	18.37	39.62	48.87	56.34	75.25
75	14.87	35	42.62	50.87	68.67
90	12.25	30.65	37.62	46.25	62.34
105	9.62	25.76	35.12	42.5	55.45
120	7.62	22.87	30.87	38.87	50.25
135	4	18.12	26.62	34.45	45.62
150	0	12.87	20.13	28.12	41.23
165	0	5.34	13.98	22	36.78
180	0	0	6.56	15.12	30.12
195	0	0	0	8.56	24.12
210	0	0	0	0	18.65
225	0	0	0	0	11.78
240	0	0	0	0	5.34
255	0	0	0	0	0
Initial rate ($\mu\text{M}/\text{m}$)	0.722	0.804	0.948	1.04	0.938

Catalyst = ZnO-TiO₂ nanoparticle (1 g/L); pH = 7.0±0.1; temperature = 30.0±0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 532 nm.

the photodegradation process is proportional to the substrate concentration in accordance with apparent first-order kinetics³⁴. When increasing the concentration from 50 μM to 120 μM the performance of degradation process is decreased. The degradation of nano ZnO-TiO₂ found to be effective and the complete degradation occurred within 190 min for 90 μM of dye solution. The complete degradation of 100 μM and 120 μM of reactive red 198 occurred within 210 and 250 min. It is due to the degradation of dye solution decreases with increase in the concentration of dye solution. When the concentration of dye molecule in aqueous solution is high, more and more dye molecules are adsorbed on the surface of nano photocatalyst. Also the substances present in the dye solution may compete for the active sites on a ZnO-TiO₂ surface or deactivate the photocatalyst and, as a result, cause a decrease in degradation of targeted dye solution. In the ZnO/TiO₂ composite, the electron transfer occurs from the conduction band of light-activated ZnO to the conduction band of light-activated TiO₂ and, conversely, hole transfer can take place from the valence band of TiO₂ to the valence band of ZnO. This efficient charge separation increases the lifetime of the charge carriers and enhances the photocatalytic efficiency of photocatalyst³⁵. From the result the photodegradation of dye solution in presence of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particle was fast and acted as an efficient photocatalyst.

Kinetic analysis :

Effect of dye concentration :

Under constant conditions of pH, catalyst weight and photon flux the effect of concentration of the dye on its photodegradability has been studied. In all the cases, plot of ‘log (C₀/C)’ vs ‘t’ shows linear straight lines which indicates that the degradation follows pseudo-first order kinetics. In $\ln(C_0/C) = kt$, where C₀ is the initial concentration, C is the concentration at any time ‘t’ and k is the observed first order rate constant. The plot of log (C₀/C) vs time for ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles for various concentrations from 50–120 μM gave a straight line as shown in the Fig. 7. The correlation constant R² best fit line was calculated to be 0.993, 0.997, 0.996, 0.991 and 0.986 for nano ZnO-TiO₂ nanoparticles. Table 6 shows

Table 6. $\log C_0/C$ and k value for the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198

Sr. No.	Time in min	$\log C_0/C$					k value				
		50 μM	75 μM	90 μM	100 μM	120 μM	50 μM	75 μM	90 μM	100 μM	120 μM
1.	0	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2.	5	0.0338	0.0244	0.0242	0.0238	0.018	0.0156	0.0112	0.0111	0.0109	0.0083
3.	10	0.0856	0.0554	0.5323	0.0554	0.0431	0.0174	0.0113	0.0108	0.0112	0.0087
4.	15	0.1341	0.0824	0.0837	0.0829	0.0683	0.0206	0.0126	0.0128	0.0127	0.0105
5.	25	0.1955	0.1306	0.1191	0.1093	0.0976	0.018	0.0121	0.0109	0.0101	0.0089
6.	35	0.2562	0.1703	0.1575	0.1538	0.1248	0.0169	0.0112	0.0103	0.0101	0.0082
7.	45	0.4194	0.2165	0.2026	0.1928	0.1517	0.0215	0.0111	0.0104	0.0098	0.0077
8.	60	0.4194	0.2681	0.2519	0.2379	0.1855	0.0161	0.1027	0.0096	0.0091	0.0091

Fig. 7. Effect of concentration of dye solution on the photocatalytic degradation of reactive red 198-kinetic study.

the $\log C_0/C$ and k value for photodegradation of reactive red 198 dye solution in the presence of nano ZnO-TiO₂ composite particles. It is found that the rate constant values of nano ZnO-TiO₂ particles decrease when increase in concentration of dye solution³⁶.

Reusability of the nanophotocatalyst :

Reusability of ZnO-TiO₂ nanocomposite for the photocatalytic degradation was also evaluated. The catalyst lifetime is an important parameter of the photocatalytic process because its use for longer period of time leads to a significant cost reduction of the treatment. For this, nanocatalyst was separated from the reactive red 198 dye solution after the completion of photodegradation process by filtration, washed with water and dried at 100 and 200 °C. It showed a drop in efficiency from 100% in 5 h to 90%. This is likely due to fouling of the catalyst and loss due to filtration. The decrease in the degradation percentage is explained by adsorption of organic inter-

mediates and by-products of the photodegradation process on the surface of the photocatalyst that influences the surface activity of the nanocatalyst³⁷.

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